

SCREENING AND IDENTIFICATION OF BROWN PLANTHOPPER RESISTANT PREBREEDING STOCKS FROM THE WILD MULTIPARENTAL POPULATION OF RICE (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Abstract

Brown planthopper (Nilaparvata lugens Stal.) is a serious pest of rice which affects most of the rice growing areas across the globe. The highly evolving nature of the pest demands for the durable resistance, for which the wide variability hidden in wild Oryza germplasm can be utilized. The introgression lines from a Multiparent Advance Generation Intercross (MAGIC) population derived from the eight parental cross of Oryza A-genome complex were screened for BPH resistance in seedling and adult plant stages. Seven lines were identified as resistance in seedling stage screening and among them; three were resistant in the adult stage also. Two of these lines were better than the resistant check (Ptb-33) used. The total phenolic content in the resistant entries were more than the susceptible entries in both seedling and adult stages, could be one of the resistance mechanisms. These prebreeding lines with resistance alleles from the wild parents can be utilized for the further improvement in cultivated rice.

Key words: Brown planthopper, MAGIC, *Oryza*, Prebreeding, Wild rice

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a major staple in the world which provides more than 20 per cent of the calorie intake of about one-third of the population (GriSp 2013). Even though the green revolution technologies increased the production in past decades, still there is a huge gap between production and the demand (Fahad et al. 2019). So, to fill this gap and ensure the global food security, the rice production must be increased by increasing production potential of the varieties and by decreasing the losses due to stresses.

Brown planthopper (*Nilaparvata lugens* Stal.) (BPH) is one of the major biotic stresses that limit the yield potential of rice causing heavy losses up to 70 per cent and the use of chemical control is uneconomical due to highly evolving nature of the pest (Sarao and Bentur 2016; Hu et al. 2018). The severity will be in an increasing trend due to the increase in atmospheric temperature which can affect the 'population metabolism' of the insect (Deutsch et al. 2018). So in order to explore the novel resistance sources, the variability of the *Oryza* germplasm should be utilized.

The importance of crop wild relatives had reached to the limelight in the recent past. In general, the cultivated plants are having lower level tolerance to different stresses which might be due to the one-dimensional selection for increased yield (Mammadov et al. 2018). In the 24 species of the *Oryza* genus, only two are cultivated. The 22 wild species with extensive and unexplored variability can be used for the improvement of the cultivated species (Shakiba and Eizenga 2014).

The most utilized species for rice improvement belongs to the 'A' genome complex which contains two cultivated species viz., *O. sativa* and *O. glaberrima* along with six wild species (Brar and Khush 2018). Among these species, *O. rufipogon* and *O. nivara* are the proven donors for BPH resistance genes (Li et al. 2001; Kumar et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2019). The major genes imparting resistance to BPH like *Bph14*, *bph24(t)*, *Bph20(t)*, *Bph21(t)* and *BPH27* are identified from *O. rufipogon* accessions (Deen et al. 2010; Li et al. 2010; Yang et al. 2012; Huang et al. 2013). Recently, a gene, *Bph34* was mapped in the introgression lines of *O. nivara* and it was a major QTL which explained 68.3% variance (Kumar et al. 2018). The other A-genome species also found to have resistance genes but are yet to be explored. So the introgression lines containing these species will be the potential sources for resistance. In this experiment, Wild Rice Multiparent Advanced Generation Intercross (Wild rice MAGIC) population derived from the cross of all eight A-genome species were explored for the BPH resistance both in seedling and adult stage.

Materials And Methods

Materials

The experimental materials primarily consists of 100 introgression lines from F_{4,5} generation of Wild Rice Multiparent Advanced

Generation Intercross (Wild rice MAGIC) population derived from the cross of eight parents (Table 1), all belong to A genome complex of the *Oryza* genus. The base material was maintained in Department of Rice, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, which was initially obtained from International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), Philippines, as a part of the project 'Wild Rice MAGIC'. For BPH screening, TN1 variety is used as susceptible check while, the resistant check used was Ptb 33.

Experimental details

The 100 entries of F_{4,5} population were screened for brown planthopper resistance in Entomology glass house at Department of Rice, TNAU, Coimbatore

Mass rearing of Brown planthopper

The initial population of brown planthopper (BPH) was collected from the fields in Department of Rice, Coimbatore. The mass multiplication was carried out at the Entomology glass house by following the methods described by Heinrichs (1985) using Taichung Native 1 (TN 1) as susceptible feeding source. The multiplication was done in oviposition cages (45 cm x 45 cm x 60 cm) made of wooden frames with door and wire mesh walls. The adults collected were released in the 35 day old plants of TN 1 in pots kept in oviposition cages. The insects were removed three days later and the plants with eggs were transferred to separate cage for the emergence of the nymphs.

Standard seed box screening for BPH

The BPH resistance at seedling stage was screened by using standard seed box screening technique (SSST) which was developed by Heinrichs (1985). The seed boxes of size 60 x 45 x 10 cm were used for screening and 20 genotypes were screened at a time in a single seed box. Each entry was sown in 20 cm long row along the width of the row. The seeds were soaked for 24 hours and then the water was drained. The seeds were then kept in dark for a day and allowed to sprout. The good pre germinated seeds were sown with equal spacing in the line, so that about 20 seedlings will be maintained for each entry. The susceptible entry TN 1 was planted at both ends and the resistant check Ptb 33 was sown in the middle of the seed box.

The first or second instar nymphs were released in the seven day old seedlings in such a way to keep the insect population at the rate of 7-8 nymphs per seedling. The insects were allowed to feed on the seedlings. The observations were taken when 90 per cent of the susceptible check showed wilting symptoms or any of the test entries shown wilting symptoms. Scoring was done based on Standard Evaluation System of rice (IRRI 2002) for BPH scoring with 0-9 scale.

Adult plant screening for BPH resistance

The entries which were found resistant in the seedling stage screening were further evaluated for adult plant resistance in terms of days to wilting. The variation in time taken for complete wilting of adult plants of different genotypes was considered as important phenotypic

screening for adult plant resistance (Kadirvel et al. 2007). The pre-germinated seeds were sown in 10 cm diameter clay pots. The 50 days old plants of the selected entries along with the resistant (Ptb 33) and susceptible (TN 1) checks were taken in three replications for the study in a completely randomized design. The seedlings were caged with cylindrical Mylar sheet cage (30 x 11 cm). Ten second instar nymphs were released in each plant and allowed to feed without any disturbances. The days taken for complete wilting of the plants were observed and mean was worked out. The analysis of variance of completely randomized experiment with three replications was done by using SPSS 16.0 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA).

Biochemical analysis - Estimation of total phenolics (mg g⁻¹)

The total phenolics of the entries advanced for adult plant resistance screening were done in both seedling stage and adult plant stage. The estimation of phenols was done by using the protocol suggested by Sadasivam and Manickam (1996). For the estimation of phenols, 500 mg of leaf sample was extracted with 10 times the volume of 80% ethanol. The homogenate was then centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 20 minutes. The supernatant was then collected in the test tube and then ethanol was evaporated by placing it in a water bath. Then the residue was dissolved in 5 ml distilled water. About 1 ml of the aliquot was taken to another test tube and made up the volume to 3 ml using distilled water. Then 0.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was added and incubated at room temperature for 3 minutes. After incubation, 2 ml of 20% sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃) was added and placed in the boiling water bath for 1 min and then cooled down by using the running tap water. The blue color developed was measured at 650 nm against a reagent blank in spectrophotometer. The total phenols in the samples were estimated using the standard curve prepared by using different concentrations of Pyro-catechol.

Results And Discussion

Brown planthopper (BPH) is one of the most destructive pests of paddy. There are several wild species in the A-genome complex which contribute alleles imparting resistance to BPH (Rongbai et al. 2010; Kumar et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2018). The earlier studies suggests that the wild species of rice is having the non-preference mechanism and they also affect the fecundity, feeding rate and growth of BPH (Jung-Tsung et al. 1986). Most of the alleles reported from A-genome complex are from *O. rufipogon*, *O. nivara* and *O. longistaminata* (Jena et al. 2006; Rongbai et al. 2010; Sarao et al. 2016; Kumar et al. 2018). So the wild rice MAGIC could contain hidden treasures of variability for BPH resistance. The 100 lines of F_{4:5} population were screened for the resistance for BPH along with their cultivated parents.

Mass screening of introgression lines was carried out by using standard seed box screening technique (SSST) for evaluating the resistance at seedling stage (Table 2). The entries found to be resistant were further studied for their resistant level at adult plant stage by estimating the days to wilt parameter (Table 3).

Standard seed box screening technique for BPH

The seedling stage resistance to brown planthopper was studied in standard seed box screening technique by following standard protocol and scoring was done (Table 2). Both the cultivated parents were recorded as moderately susceptible with the score of 7. This suggests that the alleles for the resistance came from the wild *Oryza* species possibly, *O. rufipogon*, *O. nivara* and *O. longistaminata* parents. The score of the resistant check, *O. sativa* var. PTB 33 was 3 and the susceptible check, *O. sativa* var. TN1, scored 9. There were 7 entries which were observed as resistant with a score 3 and 15 entries were moderately resistant with score of 5. There were seven entries which were highly resistant to BPH with a score of 3 which was equal to that of the resistant check, PTB-33 (Figure 1). Most of the entries were observed in moderately susceptible category. The resistant entries with minimum score of 3 identified in the seedling stage, viz. WRM 23-47-3, WRM 24-35-2, WRM 24-48-2, WRM 44-40-1, WRM 99-41-1, WRM 101-14-4 and WRM 103-7-1 were screened for adult plant resistance.

Screening for adult plant resistance for BPH

The resistant entries from the seed box screening were further subjected to the screening in the adult plant stage. The seven resistant entries identified in the seedling stage were raised in pots for the adult plant screening (Table 3). Three susceptible entries (WRM 3-35-5, WRM 6-7-1 and WRM 54-30-1) were also included with the susceptible and resistant checks for comparison. The level of resistance was assessed in terms of days to wilt parameter which was found to be an important parameter considered as a measure for adult plant resistance (Kadirvel et al. 2007). The days taken for complete wilting after the insect release was observed. The genotype WRM 24-35-2 showed the high level of resistance and took longer days to wilt (36.33 days) followed by WRM 24-48-2 (31.67 days). The susceptible check and WRM 54-30-1 were highly susceptible and wilted within 17.33 and 14.33 days after the insect release respectively. The most resistant entry, WRM 24-35-2 took more than double the number of days to wilt after insect release than the susceptible entry TN-1 and it was even better than PTB-33.

Estimation of total phenolics in the resistant entries

There were many biochemical compounds identified as factors conferring resistant to BPH from seedling to maturity stage. The phenolics compounds found to have the significant detrimental effect on many sucking insects so as the BPH (Vijaykumar et al. 2009; Nanthakumar et al. 2012; Hao et al. 2018; Kaushik et al. 2019). The phenolics content of the rice plants could increase due to the insect attack and according to the injury caused by the insect (Rani and Jyothsna 2010). Also it was already proved that the wild *Oryza* species and the introgressed lines contain comparatively more phenolic compounds when compared to cultivated rice (Chou et al. 1991; Fasahat et al. 2012a). The *O. rufipogon* and *O. longistaminata*, the parental species of this population are known to have high total phenolic contents (Xu et al. 2010; Fasahat et al. 2012b; Song et al. 2012).

The total phenols for the resistant entries were estimated in the seedling stage and adult plant stage (Table 4). Three susceptible entries, resistant and susceptible checks were also included for comparison. The study revealed that the resistant entries had more phenolics than the susceptible entries. The amount of phenolics increased with the stage of the plant. In both the stages, WRM 24-48-2 showed the highest phenolics content (0.0758 mg g⁻¹ and 0.4985 mg g⁻¹ for seedling and adult stage respectively). The lowest was observed in the genotype WRM 3-35-5 (0.0145 mg g⁻¹) in the seedling stage, while in the adult stage, WRM 6-7-1 showed the lowest value (0.1087 mg g⁻¹).

While studying the phenolic content in this population, the phenolics content in the seedling stage was lesser than the adult plant stage in all the lines. And also it was evident that the phenolics content in the susceptible entries were lower than the resistant entries in both the stages. An elevated level of phenolic content up to three times that of the susceptible check was observed in the adult stage. So it could be one of the mechanisms which impart resistance in the highly resistant entries like WRM 24-35-2. Different genes conferring resistance have different mechanisms of resistance which includes defense related modification of the cells (especially the phloem cells), production of secondary metabolites (Ji et al. 2016). Fine mapping and cloning of the genes could dissect the mechanism behind the resistance.

Several genes for resistance to BPH are reported wild relatives in several studies (Yang et al. 2004; Jena et al. 2006; Li-Hong et al. 2006; Du et al. 2009; Jena 2010; Hu et al. 2015). Identifying such introgression lines with resistant alleles from the wild will be helpful in pyramiding multiple resistant genes which could provide a durable resistance (Hu et al. 2013). Also these introgression lines can be used for mapping of novel alleles from the wild *Oryza* species as the wild parents involved in the population found to have resistant alleles for BPH (Rongbai et al. 2001; Madurangi et al. 2010; Huang et al. 2013).

Conclusion

Wild *Oryza* species are the valuable resources to broaden the genetic base of BPH resistance in rice. There were seven introgression lines derived from the wild rice MAGIC population which were highly

resistant to BPH during the seedling stage. While three introgression lines, WRM 24-35-2, WRM 24-48-2 and WRM 101-14-4 were resistant in both seedling and adult stages and WRM 24-35-2, WRM 24-48-2 performed better than the resistant check in the adult stage. The total phenolic content of these entries were more than the susceptible lines which could be one of the mechanisms of resistance. These lines are valuable prebreeding materials for the further improvement of brown planthopper resistance in cultivated rice.

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44.

45. Table 1: The list of parents of wild rice MAGIC population

Sl. No.	Species	Cultivated/ Wild	Variety/Accession No.
1.	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	Cultivated	NSICRc 222
2.	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Cultivated	CG14
3.	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Wild	80671
4.	<i>O. barthii</i>	Wild	106017
5.	<i>O. nivara</i>	Wild	101508
6.	<i>O. meridionalis</i>	Wild	105290
7.	<i>O. glumaepatula</i>	Wild	105672
8.	<i>O. longistaminata</i>	Wild	110405

R-Resistant, MR- Moderately resistant, MS- Moderately susceptible, S-Susceptible

Table 2: Resistant and moderately resistant F_{4:5} MAGIC progenies for brown planthopper*

Sl.No	Progenies	Scores	Resistant category
	WRM 5-26-3	5	MR
	WRM 17-9-2	5	MR
	WRM 23-25-5	5	MR
	WRM 23-47-3	3	R
	WRM 24-35-2	3	R
	WRM 24-48-2	3	R
	WRM 27-24-1	5	MR
	WRM 30-6-2	5	MR
	WRM 31-21-5	5	MR
	WRM 37-1-4	5	MR
	WRM 38-1-3	5	MR

Sl.No	Progenies	Scores	Resistant category
	WRM 40-15-2	5	MR
	WRM 41-14-5	5	MR
	WRM 44-40-1	3	R
	WRM 50-27-5	5	MR
	WRM 50-45-2	5	MR
	WRM 72-4-4	5	MR
	WRM 72-15-1	5	MR
	WRM 73-38-4	5	MR
	WRM 99-41-1	3	R
	WRM 101-14-4	3	R
	WRM 103-7-1	3	R
	<i>O. glaberrima</i> var.CG14	7	MS
	<i>O. sativa</i> var. NSICRc222	7	MS
	<i>O. sativa</i> var.ptb33	3	R
	<i>O. sativa</i> var.TN1	9	S

*Only selected progenies, cultivated parents and checks are included

Table 3: Adult plant screening of selected progenies of F_{4:5} generation for brow planthopper resistance

Sr. No.	Entry	Days to wilt
1.	TN1*	17.33±1.76 ^{ef}
2.	Ptb33**	28.33±1.85 ^b
3.	WRM 3-35-5	20.00±1.00^{def}
4.	WRM 6-7-1	22.67±1.33^{cde}
5.	WRM 23-47-3	26.67±0.67 ^{bcd}
6.	WRM 24-35-2	36.33±6.57 ^a
7.	WRM 24-48-2	31.67±0.67 ^{ab}
8.	WRM 44-40-1	25.33±0.33 ^{bcd}
9.	WRM 54-30-1	14.33±1.86^f
10.	WRM 99-41-1	24.33±0.67 ^{bcd}
11.	WRM 101-14-4	28.00±1.52 ^b
12.	WRM 103-7-1	22.67±1.20 ^{cde}

*Susceptible check, **Resistant check, Bold letters indicates susceptible entries

Table 4: Variation in total phenolics content of selected progenies of F_{4:5} generation in seedling and adult stages

Sr. No.	Entry	Total phenolics content (mg g ⁻¹)	
		Seedling stage (7 DAS)	Adult plant stage (50 DAS)
1.	TN1*	0.0425	0.1210
2.	Ptb33**	0.0542	0.2122
3.	WRM 3-35-5	0.0145	0.1545
4.	WRM 6-7-1	0.0189	0.1087
5.	WRM 23-47-3	0.0222	0.2355
6.	WRM 24-35-2	0.0331	0.2599
7.	WRM 24-48-2	0.0758	0.4985
8.	WRM 44-40-1	0.0680	0.3687
9.	WRM 54-30-1	0.0545	0.1285
10.	WRM 99-41-1	0.0453	0.2114
11.	WRM 101-14-4	0.0441	0.2483
12.	WRM 103-7-1	0.0425	0.1210

Data presented are means from three replicates with standard errors

*Susceptible check, **Resistant check, Bold letters indicates susceptible entries

Figure 1: The variation in brown plant hopper resistance reaction in F_{4:5} progenies

